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635 Santali

Source:

Neukom, Lukas. (2001). Santali.

München: Lincom (Languages of the World/Materials, 323)

UB: 01 A 2003 15423

-> almost all information and examples are taken from this grammar; exceptions are noted

Bodding, P.O. (1930). Materials for a Santali grammar, I (mostly phonetic).

Dumka: Santal Mission of the Northern Churches

MPI: PL 4563 BOD 1930

Sebeok, T. (1943). Phonemic system of Santali

Journal of the American Oriental Society 63:66-67

Zide, Norman Herbert. (1958). Final Stops in Korcu and Santali

Indian Linguistics 19/1:44-48

I. Language Profile:

Population: 5,959,000 in India (1997). Population total all countries: 6,156,260.

Region: Assam; Bihar; Orissa; Tripura; West Bengal; Mizoram. Also spoken in Bangladesh, Bhutan, Nepal.

Alternate names: Hor, Har, Satar, Santhali, Sandal, Sangtal, Santal, Sentali, Samtali, Santhiali, Sonthal

Dialects: Karmali (Khole), Kamari-Santali, Lohari-Santali, Manjhi, Paharia, Mahali (Mahili, Mahli). Close to Ho and Mundari.

Classification: Austro-Asiatic, Munda, North Munda, Kherwari, Santali

Language use: Official language.

Language development: Literacy rate in first language: 10% to 30%. Literacy rate in second language: 25% to 50%. Taught in primary schools.

Roman and Oriya scripts; Roman script in Bangladesh. Magazines. Dictionary. Grammar. Bible: 1914–2001.

Comments: Santali is a Scheduled Tribe in India. Agriculturalists; laborers. Hindu, traditional religion, Christian.

Also spoken in:

Bangladesh: 157,000 in Bangladesh (2001 Johnstone and Mandryk). Ethnic

population: 42,698.
Alternate names: Hor, Satar, Santhali, Sandal, Sangtal, Santal, Har, Sonthal
Dialects: Karmali (Khole), Kamari-Santali, Lohari-Santali, Paharia, Mahali (Mahle) Manjhi.
Language use: Positive language attitude.
Language development: Literacy rate in first language: 50%.

Nepal:

Population: 40,260 in Nepal (2001 census). Ethnic population: 42,698.
Region: Koshi Zone, Morang District; Mechi Zone, Jhapa District.
Alternate names: Satar, Santhali, Santhal, Sonthal, Sandal, Sangtal, Santal, Sentali, Saini, Hor, Har
Language use: 1,339 second-language Satar speakers and 559 second-language Santhal speakers (1991 census). Some bilingualism in Maithili and Nepali.
Language development: Literacy rate in first language: Few. Literacy rate in second language: Few.
Comments: Recognized as an official nationality by the Government of Nepal. Hunter-gatherers; agriculturalists. Hindu, Christian.

Loan Words: most from Indo-Aryan languages, from Bengali or from Hindi - some of them with origin in Arabic or Persian

Indo Aryan loans are found in all domains of the vocabulary

II. Morpheme Types:

i. stem

ii. postposed restricted formative

- restricted to lexemes in argument position: number, class, possessor, focus/topic

oʀakʔ-ko-re-ge
house-PL-LOC-FOC
'it is in the houses that ...'

- restricted to lexemes in predicate position: TAM, voice, pronominal arguments, sentential modality

dal-leʔ-a-e
strike-PLUP.ACT-IND-3sS
'he had struck'

iii. postposed unrestricted formative

- case marker: attaches to lexemes in argument position indicating case; and to lexemes in predicate position to form subordinated adverbial clauses

adɔ-ɪŋ eskar-te kœ-y-e-re ma pasɕʔ-e pʰeɾa-y-ɪŋ.

then-1sS alone-INST ask-y-3sO-LOC MOD perhaps-3sS resist-y-1sO
 'If I ask him myself alone, he might resist me.' (expresses condition)

– topic marker -dɔ attach to arguments, adverbial phrases, predicates

a. ona saɖe aŋjom-te uni tərup²-dɔ-e bɔtɔr-en-te
 that.INAN sound hear-CONV that.AN leopard-TOP-3sS
 ona bir-k^hɔn ɲir-oɖok-en-te eɬak²
 that.INAN forest-ABL run-come.out-PST.MID-CONV other
 bir-te-y-e ucəɾ-ok²-kan-tahẽkan-a
 forest-ALL-y-3sS move-MID-IPFV-COP.PST-IND

'When the leopard heard that noise, he was frightened, came running out of the forest and went to another forest.'

b. onka-e kuli-y-et²-ko-a, ar mẽt²ãhã-sen-e
 like.that-3sSask-y-IPFV.ACT-3pO-IND and face-ALL-3sS
 bɛŋgɛt²-rakap²-a-ko-kan-dɔ, sanam-ge əɖi-tɛt²
 look-raise-APPL-3pO-IPFV-TOP all-FOC much-EMPH
 bəpuɾic² mẽt²ãhã-ko ɲɛl-ok²-kan
 helpless face-3pS see-MID-IPFV

'He was asking them that and looking up towards their faces: all of them were looking totally helpless.'

– focus marker -ge: can be added to any constituent of the sentence

– „clitics“: subject pronominal clitics

- attach to the word immediately preceding the verb
- when they are attached to the verb form itself, they occupy the final position (but this is rare)

ba-e cala-k²-a
 NEG-3sS go-MID-IND
 'He won't go.'

iv. infixes

- occur in derivation of „nouns“ (lexemes used in argument position)
 - -nV- or -tV-, where V is a copy of the preceding vowel
 - but this process is not productive anymore and rather rare
- osar 'to be broad' > onosar 'breadth'

v. particles

express a certain mode, doubt, exhortative

nui ma ɲn-ren hɔɾ kan-e,
 this.AN MOD 1s-GEN.AN person COP-3sS

ar am ma-m peṛa hɔɾ kan
 and 2s MOD-2sS friend person COP
 'This is my wife and you are just a friend.'

Note:

noun and verb distinction is debateable – so most of the lexemes appear in both argument and predicate position carrying the affixes according to its function as argument or predicate (extends also to loans), however there is a relatively large group of lexemes which occur only in predicate position

ex.: dare 'tree; becoming a tree, grow'

- a. dare-khɔn-e ɲurhə-y-en-te moka rəput[?]-en-ta-e-a
 tree-ABL-3sS f all-y-PST.MID-INST forearm break-PST.MID-POSS-3s-IND
 'When he fall down from a tree, he broke his forearm.'
- b. nɛs səuɾi-dɔ bes dare-akan-a
 this.year thatching.grass-TOP well grow-PF.MID-IND
 'This year the thatching-grass has grown well.'

III. Syllable

light syllables: (C)V (status of glottal plosive is not discussed)

- ex.: ti 'hand'
 ic[?] 'shit'

heavy syllables: (C)VX

X is filled either by a vowel (-> diphtong) or by a consonant (CVC)

- ex.: dea 'back'
 hɛc[?] 'come'

- no super-heavy syllables
- no initial C-clusters
- non-word final syllables can end in two consonants
- stems are mono- or bisyllabic, rarely trisyllabic

following syllabic structures have been attested (words with more than two syllables are rather rare):

- CV.CV
- CV.CVV
- CV.CVC
- CVC.CVC
- CVCC.CV
- V.CV
- V.CVV

V.CVC
VC.CV
VC.CVV
VC.CVC
VV.CV
VV.CVV

IV. Phonotactics

Consonants

- /ŋ/, /ɾ/, semi-vowels /y, w/ do not occur in word-initial position
- /h/, glides /w, y/ do not occur in word-final position
- aspirated consonants do not occur at the end of a syllable
- within the same stress unit, only one aspirate occurs [Bodding(1930)]
- sequences of three consonants in the structure CVCC.CV always contain a homorganic nasal+plosive cluster
ex.: send.ra 'hunt'
- in word-final position only the consonant sequence nasal+C may occur [Sebeok (1943)]
- final consonants are lengthened if the last syllable bears stress
- Where foreign words ending in more than one C are adopted, one of the following ways is followed [Bodding(1930)]:
 - a) a vowel is introduced dissolving the consonant combination
 - b) one of the consonants is omitted
 - c) a vowel is attached at the end (generally the last vowel of the word)
 - d) if the foreign word has a somewhat reduced vowel in the last syllable, this vowel is strengthened, sometimes in its original place, sometimes transposed to the end
 - e) when the final consonant-nasal combination is not homorganic and the combination is not treated in accordance with one of the rules just mentioned, the nasal may be attempted rendered simply by nasalization of the preceding vowel
 - f) in some very few cases the combination is attempted kept
- distribution of glottalized plosives is restricted to stem-final position, where the voiceless and voiced series of plosives tend to be neutralised
- some exceptions which allow non-glottalized plosives in syllable-final position - most of them are Indo-Aryan loans, few of Munda origin
- morphologically conditioned alternation of the glottalized plosives with their voiced counterparts, does not apply when a subject pronominal clitic attaches:
 - a) when the verb is used in the NPST with no object pronominal suffixes (i.e. in front of the indicative -a or the middle marker -ok?)
ex.: dɛcʔ 'pick' > dɛj-a-e 'he will pick (flowers)'
 - b) when a vowel-initial pronominal suffix follows (-ij 1.SG and -e 3.SG), this

applies to TAM suffixes ending in -t' as well)
ex.: ruhet' 'scold' > ruhed-ij-a-e'he will scold me'

- c) when the verb is in the imperative, used transitively
ex.: beret' 'get up' > bered-me 'raise'

Vowels

- no hiatus [Bodding (1930)]: resolution is glide insertion or diphthongisation
- sequences of more than two vowels are possible but not within the same syllable
ex.: eae 'seven'
even sequence VVVVVV [Sebeok (1943); Bodding (1930)]: kəeaeae 'He will ask for him'
--> sequence is dissolved so that the vowels are pronounced as belonging to different syllables
- the vowel of monosyllabic words (as opposed to the vowel of monosyllables as suffixes) is generally long

V. Phonological Processes

i. Assimilation (anticipating)

n > ŋ / _{t, d, tʰ, dʰ}

ex.: ɔŋdɛ 'there (location)' vs. ɔntɛ 'there (destination)'

ii. Glide insertion

glides [w, y] are inserted when vowel-initial suffixes are attached to vowels of the same quality

ex.: ho-y-okʰ-a-e

become-y-MID-IND-3sS

'he will become'

- not inserted if a word ending in vowel is followed by a word starting with a vowel [Bodding (1930)]

iii. Vowel Harmony

- can be described by three sets: a vowel tends to occur exclusively with the members of the same set:

Set 1: i, ə, u

Set 2: e, a, o

Set 3: ɛ, ɔ

- the restrictions to avoid vowels of different sets within the same stress unit (i.e. a mono- or disyllabic word or part of a word, not necessarily mono-morphemic –

speakers can redefine the stress unit in case of emphasis) are not all of equal rigidity, the following remarks are in order:

- of the two central vowels /ə, a/: /ə/ but never /a/ co-occurs with /i, u/ - this does not mean that /a/ and /ə/ are allophones
- /a/ but never /ə/ co-occurs with /e, ε, o, ɔ/
- the high vowels /i, u/ do not normally co-occur with the mid vowels of the same position (/i/ is not found together with /e, ε/, whereas /u/ is not found together with /o, ɔ/
- /e, o/ are not combined with /ε, ɔ/, although diphthongs /ɔe/ and /εo/ are found
- /ε/ is found rarely together with /a/ in the same stress unit
- harmony does not take place with disyllabic bases ending in a consonant, nor does it happen with infixes which commence with a consonant, because in these cases we have two or more stress-units [Bodding (1930)]

VI. Stress

- in disyllabic stems stress falls on the first syllable, however if the first syllable is light and the second heavy, stress falls on the second syllable

Bodding (1930):

- stress unit is mono- or disyllabic, rarely trisyllabic
- no fixed general rule for placement of stress
- stress may be anywhere within the stress unit, only that in the same word it will remain in the same place, except:
 - affixes and adpositions (=case suffixes according to Neucom, 2001) will not affect the original placement of stress in the base, except as to strengthen or weakening the degree, provided that the affixes and adpositions do not melt into one stress unit with the word
- monosyllabic words (apart from affixes): have stress; generally have a long vowel except words ending in a glottalized consonant
- disyllabic words: stress on either the first or the second syllable – generally heavy syllables attract stress, tendency to draw stress on the ultima, especially if the last syllable has a glottalized consonant as final
 - disyllabic words formed by reduplication of a monosyllabic base (consisting of a C followed by a V) have a slightly perceptible preponderance of stress on ultima, except where a nasal has been inserted between the two syllables – giving preponderance of quantity to the first syllable
 - disyllabics formed from monosyllabics by infixing a consonant or by reduplication of the first two segments have stress on ultima
 - disyllabics formed from other disyllabics by inserting a consonant after the medial one may keep the stress in the original place
 - disyllabics with final vowel and the same vowel in both syllables generally have stress on the ultima

- genuine disyllabics, consisting of two vowels and a medial consonant, receive stress on the last syllable – but if a nasal is inserted before the medial consonant, stress falls on the first syllable
 - if one syllable is comparatively longer than the other, this syllable receives stress
 - if there are two diphthongs in the word (each in one syllable) the result may be two stress units
- trisyllabic words: a) formed by reduplication or b) adopted from other languages
- a) dissolved into two stress units:
- heavier stress on the last syllable as the second stress unit; weaker one on the first stress unit (=first two syllable)
 - within the first (secondary) stress unit, (secondary) stress is distributed according to the nature of the syllables (see rules for disyllabics)
- b) stress varies → general rule: forming two stress units '[σσ][σ]
- polysyllabic words: dissolved into stress units with at most two syllables each
- compounds:
- compounds not representing a new single concept have stress according to which part is to be emphasized
 - in simple compounds where both parts are of equal importance, separate stress units are the rule
 - compounds consisting of a single word plus a prefixed privative particle are also generally two stress units; but if the single word is monosyllabic, mostly only one stress unit with stress on the privative; if it is disyllabic also only one stress unit possible with stress on the penultimate of the compound
- suffixes:
- suffixes can receive stress and constitute a proper stress unit, especially when followed by other stress-less parts of speech
 - when a monosyllabic suffix is added the stress may be moved to the suffix
 - when added to disyllabic words usually dissolved in two stress units

VII. Reduplication

- partial: not described; examples show reduplication of a CVC-root, reduplicant is CV

ex.: uni maejiu-dɔ tanman-e ɲɛ-ɲɛl-kan-a
 that.AN woman-TOP carefully-3sS RED-see-IPFV-IND
 'The woman is looking carefully.'

- total: signals intensified or continued action or it indicates that the action nearly happened, but did not finally

ex.: hola-n-ak² edre ma teheṅ-dɔ
yesterday-ATTR-NMLZ.INAN anger MOD today-TOP
kusiã dal-dal-eṅ-me!
as.you.like beat-RED-1sO-2sS

'(In return for) yesterday's anger please beat me today as you like.'